

THE USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPING COLLEGE STUDENTS' COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: *The article discusses the use of information technology in the process of English language competence formation among college students. The focus is on the use of multimedia resources and digital platforms such as Book Creator to increase motivation and learning effectiveness. A five-step system of exercises is presented, including informational, applied, transformational, communicative and creative blocks. Each of these stages is aimed at the consistent development of students' language skills. The use of digital technologies contributes to the formation of competencies in reading, writing, speaking and listening, as well as develops critical thinking and communication skills. The importance of integrating interactive tools into the educational process to create a dynamic language environment is emphasized. Thus, the introduction of information technology is a key factor in improving the quality of English language teaching.*

Keywords: *information technology, language competence, multimedia technologies, digital platforms, communication skills, Book Creator, foreign language.*

Information technology plays an important role in the development of language competence of college students. Modern digital tools and online resources allow teachers to significantly improve the learning process, making it more interactive and effective.

A large group of scholars, among them J. Raven, I.A. Zimnaya, A.K. Markova and A.V. Khutorsky differentiate the term “competence” as “knowledge”, “skills”, and “abilities”. According to Khutorsky competence is the measure, a requirement that is previously set before the student acquires knowledge. Khutorsky points out that competence is formed by the individual qualities of the student and the minimum work experience [1].

The environment for college students requires learning that allows the student to navigate the communicative space. Therefore, the learning of students should be associated with activities that are personally significant for students' communication. This process determines the motivational use of speech as a tool in the field of

linguistic communication. In the process, the goal, form, and means of educational activity of students are as close as possible to real situations of communication and speech activity with specific specificity. The purpose of this process is the appropriate means of communication and expected results. Kostyukova and Morozova also noted in their work that it is necessary to create special conditions for learning. One of these special cases is the use of multimedia technologies in the educational process [2].

The term “information technology” in its modern sense first appeared in a 1958 article published in the Harvard Business Review. Its authors, Harold J. Leavitt and Thomas L. Whisler, noted that “this new technology does not yet have a single generally accepted name [3].

Informative technologies nowadays play an important role in developing language competence. With the rapid advancement of digital tools and online resources, educators have an array of options to enhance language learning experiences for students [4].

Additionally, multimedia elements like audio recordings or videos can be incorporated to cater to diverse learning styles and enhance engagement.

In English language education, the integration of information technologies has emerged as a potent tool for enhancing students' competencies. This article explores the utilization of Informative technologies, particularly focusing on a methodical approach that integrates materials from "Aspect 10" [5], a school textbook, along with methodical modal. The assignment system is based on five Steps of mastering students` competence: Step 1 – Informative block of assignments; Step 2 – Application Block of assignments; Step 3 – Transformation block of assignments; Step 4 – Communicative block of assignments; Step 5 – Creative Block of assignments. Each step corresponds to a specific group of tasks.

1. Information Block

This initial step is designed to provide students with foundational knowledge and comprehension of the language. These could include reading passages, vocabulary lists, and grammar explanations. First Step includes the following assignments:

-Assignment 1. Warming up activities. discussion questions

In this task, students are typically engaged in preparing for further discussion of a topic or text. They can reflect on issues, discuss them in pairs or groups, and share opinions and ideas.

-Assignment 2. Read the text and write out new vocabulary

In this assignment, students read a text and then write down new vocabulary or unfamiliar words they encounter in the text.

-Assignment 3. Read and learn the new vocabulary and their definitions.

2. Application Block

In the attached block, students apply the concepts they have learned in practice. They perform exercises: fill in blanks, compose sentences, and participate in virtual situations. This helps to consolidate knowledge and improve understanding. Digital platforms provide interactivity, instant feedback, and personalized learning. Second Step includes the following assignments:

- Assignment 1. Fill in the missing words using words from the table

Students must use words from the table provided to fill in the gaps in the text, making the text coherent and meaningful.

- Assignment 2. Match the words/phrases (1-8) with their meanings (a-h). E.g. 1-b,...

Students must analyze the meanings and relate them to the corresponding words/phrases.

- Assignment 3. Label the pictures with the words from the active vocabulary

This assignment asks students to assign labels from an active vocabulary to images.

3. Transformation Block

The Transformation block develops students' ability to manipulate language structures and creatively express ideas through sentence transformation, paraphrasing, and generalization. These exercises develop understanding, analytical thinking, and creativity. Technology supports this through paraphrasing tools, grammar checking, and collaboration platforms. Third Step includes the following assignments:

- Assignment 1. Make up 4 questions about the text you read and prepare answers to them

In this assignment, students must read a text and come up with four questions regarding the content and details of the text. They must then prepare answers to these questions based on the text they read.

- Assignment 2. Read the text and give detailed answers to questions

This Assignment asks students to read a text and then provide detailed answers to questions related to the content of the text.

- Assignment 3. Combine the sentences given on the left and the right sides of the columns to get related statements

In this assignment, students must combine sentences on the left and right to create related statements or a story.

4. Communication Block

Effective communication plays a crucial role in language learning. Students actively participate in interactive exercises such as summarizing, retelling, and discussing stories. Digital platforms, including forums, video calls, and messaging apps, facilitate real-time practice. Engaging in collaborative projects, debates, and role-plays fosters active involvement and strengthens interpersonal skills. The Fourth Step includes the following tasks.

- Assignment 1. Convey the main content of the text using 5 sentences from the text.

These sentences should be key to understanding the plot and main events of the work.

- Assignment 2. Work in groups and make up the plan of the story

In this assignment, students work in groups to create an outline for a story or story.

- Assignment 3. Review the text and write it in detail retelling based on key phrases and expressions. Retell the text for your group mates according to plan

5. Creative Block

In the final stage, students develop creativity and critical thinking through open-ended assignments. They create stories, prepare essays and presentations, expressing thoughts and arguing their ideas. Digital tools such as multimedia and VR help them unleash their imagination and express themselves in English.

- Assignment 1. Create an alternative ending of each story.

- Assignment 2. Make-up own story on the same theme.

In this assignment, students work in groups to create an outline for a story or story.

- Assignment 3. Make up a dialogue between A and B and dramatize it.

- Assignment 4. Write an essay on the following topics.

In this assignment, students are required to write an essay on given topics. They are required to describe and reveal their thoughts, argue their point of view, or provide facts and evidence to support the chosen topic.

The development of a five-step exercise system using information technology represents a holistic approach to language learning by college students. Step-by-step learning of the material allows students to complete various language tasks aimed at

developing different aspects of language proficiency. From basic knowledge to creative expression, each stage contributes to the formation of key language skills.

The integration of information technologies, particularly through platforms like Book Creator, offers a dynamic and effective approach to developing language competence among college students. By incorporating multimedia elements and interactive tasks, educators can create engaging learning experiences that supply to diverse learning styles and foster essential language skills.

Through systematic progression from foundational knowledge to creative expression, students engage with language tasks that enhance comprehension, practical application, critical thinking, and communication skills. Moreover, the autonomy and creativity afforded by digital tools empower students to take ownership of their learning journey and express themselves authentically in English.

In conclusion, the utilization of information technologies in language education presents huge opportunities for enhancing students' competencies in English. As technology continues to evolve, innovative platforms like Book Creator will play a pivotal role in shaping the future of language learning, offering dynamic and engaging solutions for educators and students alike.

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